

DETERMINATION OF VISCOELASTIC PROPERTIES OF ANISOTROPIC COMPOSITE BY ULTRASONIC WAVES

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ABSTRACT

Ultrasonic testing has become the method of choice for the determination of viscoelastic properties of anisotropic media. This procedure works better than the usual way of testing materials because of classical difficulties (the need to have a lot of samples, of axis test) which are weeded out. The method is based on an analysis of the perturbation of a plane harmonic wave through a composite slab. The transit time (different wave velocities between the composite and a coupling medium) gives the storage moduli of the composite material, wave attenuation gives the loss moduli. The ultrasonic tests, required to completely characterize all nine complex moduli of anisotropic materials, are performed. The tests are conducted using contact and immersion transducers at normal incidence to identify the dilatational and shear complex moduli (C_{ij} , $i = 1, \dots, 6$). To determine coupling complex moduli (C_{ij} , $i \neq j$) we use immersion transducers with mode conversion to generate the required waves (oblique incidence and quasi-transverse waves). First and second invariant components of the complex stiffness matrix are helpful and necessary in determining in practice the coupling complex moduli of viscoelastic composites. Experimental set-up are presented.

INTRODUCTION

Wave propagation in anisotropic media has been extensively studied and used in non destructive testing and has become an outstanding method for the quality assurance of advanced materials. However one rarely uses wave propagation to determine elastic or viscoelastic behaviour of anisotropic material and to determine storage and loss moduli of materials. The fundamental properties of wave propagation in composite materials have been analyzed by Auld [1], Kline [2], where's Schoenberg et al [3], Krautkramer et al. [4], Kriz et al [5], Schreiber et al [6], Toshiyuki et al [7] describe experimental procedures.

The common acceptance of an orthotropic model of composite viscoelastic behavior means that nine independent complex components of the stiffness matrix are required for the complete determination of the material : six diagonal terms which can be easily obtained from on-axis measurements. The determination of the off-diagonal terms using through- transmission pulse

technique involves off-axis bulk wave velocity measurements leading to optimization procedure. For each obliquely direction of wave propagation the first and second invariant of the complex stiffness tensor are computed and the best fit of these invariant can be found by choosing the minimum of the root mean square. A new stiffness tensor (or matrix) is calculated and then one starts again. The process stops when the stiffness matrix does not change (variation must not exceed 2%).

THEORETICAL CONSIDERATIONS

In material characterization ultrasonic techniques are introduced to obtain the complex stiffness terms of orthotropic media from velocity and attenuation measurements. Before discussing the optimization process, it is first useful to review quickly the concept of velocity and attenuation. A phase harmonic displacement wave $U(x,t)$, propagating in the direction v ($|v|=1$), is defined by

$$U(x,t) = AP \exp [i (\omega t - \tilde{k} \cdot v x)] \quad , \quad (i^2 = -1) \tag{1}$$

where $x = (x_i)$ are the spatial coordinates, A the magnitude of the wave, P the polarization vector ($|P|=1$) and ω the circular frequency. The complex wave number \tilde{k} may be represented as:

$$\tilde{k} = k - i \alpha \tag{2}$$

α is the attenuation of the wave and $v = \omega / k$ the phase velocity. Relationships between stiffness and ultrasonic velocity are obtained by replacing the displacements given by Eqn. (1), in the equations of motion (see ref. [2]) this operation leads to equations

$$\{ \tilde{k}^2 \bar{c}_{mnpq}(\omega) v_n v_q - \rho \omega^2 \delta_{mp} \} P_p = 0 \quad , m = 1, 2, 3 \tag{3}$$

where $\bar{c}(\omega) = (\bar{c}_{mnpq}(\omega))$ is the complex stiffness tensor of the composite materials

$$(\bar{c}_{mnpq}(\omega)) = (\underset{\substack{\uparrow \\ \text{storage modulus}}}{c'_{mnpq}}(\omega)) + (\underset{\substack{\uparrow \\ \text{loss modulus}}}{c''_{mnpq}}(\omega))$$

ρ the mass density and $\delta = (\delta_{pq})$ the kronecker tensor. Equation (3) may be written as

$$|\bar{\Gamma}_{pr} - \bar{\lambda}_{pr}| P_r = 0 \quad , p = 1, 2, 3 \tag{4}$$

which is known as Christoffel equations

$$\bar{\Gamma}_{pr}(\omega) = \bar{c}_{pnrq}(\omega) v_n v_q \tag{5}$$

is the acoustical (or Christffel) tensor whose eigenvalues $\bar{\lambda}$ depend on phase velocity and on attenuation α :

$$\bar{\lambda} = \frac{\rho v^2}{[1 - \frac{i\alpha v}{\omega}]^2}, \quad i^2 = -1 \quad (6)$$

The Christoffel tensor is developed in various studies [2-3]. The general test principle is summarized on table 1.

Table 1. Scheme for testing composite materials by ultrasonic method

Diagonal terms: The diagonal complex moduli are obtained by measuring the bulk velocities of propagation waves along the symmetry axes.

$$\bar{c}_{pq}(f) = \bar{\lambda}_{pq}(f), \quad q = 1, 2, \dots, 6 \quad (7)$$

f is the frequency and the 6×6 stiffness matrix $\{\bar{c}\} = \{\bar{c}_{pq}\}$ is linked to the Stiffness tensor by the classical relations [2]. This procedure is not discussed here. **Off-diagonal terms:** The numerical values of the components \bar{c}_{pq} of the complex stiffness matrix ($p \neq q$) are obtained via the propagation of quasi-longitudinal and quasi-transverse waves [2,3] by the relationship:

$$\bar{c}_{pq} = \frac{1}{v_p v_q} \sqrt{\bar{c}_{pp} v_p^2 - \bar{G}_{pq}} \sqrt{\bar{c}_{qq} v_q^2 - \bar{G}_{pq}} \quad (8)$$

$p = 1, 2, 3, q = 1, 2, 3, p \neq q$. When the propagation takes place at an angle from the elastic symmetry axes, \bar{G}_{pq} is the complex shear modulus in the (p, q) plane. The directional dependence of the off-diagonal complex stiffnesses \bar{c}_{pq} Eqn.(8) renders conventional averaging techniques inappropriate. The approach consist of selecting the maximum $\bar{\lambda}_{pq}$ values ($p=1, 2, 3, q = 1, 2, 3, p \neq q$). For p and q fixed, ($p = 1, q = 2$ for example Fig.(1), the off-diagonal components $\bar{c}_{pq}^{(n)}$ are obtained from relation (8), $n = 1, 2, \dots, N$ denotes the number of measurements in obliquely direction ($\alpha = \alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_{N_3}$). Then for each value of α_n ($n = 1, 2, \dots, N_3$) first and second scalar invariant $\bar{I}_1^{(n)}, \bar{I}_2^{(n)}, \bar{J}_1^{(n)}, \bar{J}_2^{(n)}$ are determined from the complex complex $\bar{c}_{pq}^{(n)}$ expressed in the $(1', 2', 3')$ coordinate system (Fig.(1) & Eqn.(9)).

Figure 1. Propagation of obliquely wave in the plane (1,2).

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{I}_1^{(n)} &= \frac{3\bar{c}_{11}^{r(n)} + 3\bar{c}_{22}^{r(n)} + 2\bar{c}_{12}^{r(n)} + 4\bar{c}_{66}^{r(n)}}{8} \\
 \bar{I}_2^{(n)} &= \frac{\bar{c}_{11}^{r(n)} + \bar{c}_{22}^{r(n)} - 2\bar{c}_{12}^{r(n)} + 4\bar{c}_{66}^{r(n)}}{8} \\
 \bar{J}_1^{(n)} &= \frac{\sqrt{|\bar{c}_{11}^{r(n)} - \bar{c}_{22}^{r(n)}|^2 + 4|\bar{c}_{16}^{r(n)} + \bar{c}_{26}^{r(n)}|^2}}{2} \\
 \bar{J}_2^{(n)} &= \frac{\sqrt{|\bar{c}_{11}^{r(n)} + \bar{c}_{22}^{r(n)} - 2\bar{c}_{12}^{r(n)} - 4\bar{c}_{66}^{r(n)}|^2 + 16|\bar{c}_{26}^{r(n)} + \bar{c}_{16}^{r(n)}|^2}}{8}
 \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

The complex stiffness components can be calculated Eqn.(9) from the mean values $\bar{I}_1, \bar{I}_2, \bar{J}_1, \bar{J}_2$ of the four invariants

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{c}_{11} &= \bar{I}_1 + \bar{J}_1 + \bar{J}_2 \\
 \bar{c}_{22} &= \bar{I}_1 - \bar{J}_1 + \bar{J}_2 \\
 \bar{c}_{12} &= \bar{I}_1 - 2\bar{I}_2 - \bar{J}_2 \\
 \bar{c}_{66} &= \bar{I}_2 - \bar{J}_2
 \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

with these new values of stiffness one starts again to compute the invariants Eqn.(8) and the process stops when the R.M.S (Root mean square) between the invariants and their mean value is minimum. From this values of the complex stiffness components one begins a new optimization process with another values of p and q (p=1, q=3 then p=2, q=3, then p=1, q=2 etc). The process stops when the complex stiffness matrix does not change, i.e. the variation must not exceed 2% Fig.(2).

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The experimental procedure to obtain the velocity and the attenuation of waves propagating through a specimen of composite material is summarize in figure 3. It is interesting to note that the **Echo technique** cancels the effects of the coupling medium and gives the attenuation α with a good agreement, but it is a thickly operation. Contact technique Fig.(4) gives the diagonal complex stiffness terms and immersion technique the off - diagonal terms Fig.(5)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The set of experimental results is concerned with ensuring the validity of the method of optimization. Diagonal and off-diagonal terms are found from a series of measurements on a glass /epoxy laminated composite ($0^0, \pm 45^0$). Each layer is a fiber reinforced composite supposed to be elastic (loss moduli of stiffness vanish). The composite geometry is illustrated in figure (6) with the fiber reinforcement in the (1,3) plane. Measurement are mentioned in Table 2, the direction 2 is normal to the layer Fig.(6). In the optimization process, each partial calculation (values of k in figure 2) is obtained from 2 or 3 iterations (k=2 or 3) and the stiffness does not change (variation < 2%) after 13 steps (6 iterations for the 2, 3 plane and 7 iterations for the 2, 3 plane). Stiffnesses results are given in Table 3 and it is interesting to note that invariant technique is closer than curve fitting process on slowness curves for $c_{11}, c_{22}, c_{66}, c_{12}, c_{55}$.

Figure 2. Optimization of the off-diagonal components of the complex stiffness matrix

Figure 3. Schematic diagram used to test phase velocity and attenuation of waves by transmission technique

Table 2. Velocities of wave propagating in a laminated glass/epoxy composite depicted in Fig.(6) (Volume fraction of each layer : 0.33, mass density $\rho = 2078 \text{ kg/m}^3$).

Wave propagating in plane (1,2)						
Incident angle (degrees)	27	31	36	41	46	50
α Fig.(1) (degrees)	45.8	53.1	61.2	68.4	75.2	80.5
Velocity (m/s)	2370	2329	2237	2127	2016	1931
Wave propagating in plane (2,3)						
Incident angle (degrees)	26	31	37	36	41	
α Fig.(1) (degrees)	39.8	48.6	50.3	57.3	64.9	
Velocity (m/s)	2190	2184	2179	2147	2070	

A rather large discrepancy can be observed on the elastic constants c_{22}, c_{33}, c_{44} . Optimization invariants process may be improved if wave velocity would be available in the three planes (1,2), (1,3), (2,3).

Table 3. Stiffness components (Gpa) of an glass/epoxy composite

	C_{11}	C_{22}	C_{33}	C_{12}	C_{23}	C_{44}	C_{55}
Measurements	41.7	25.5	32.1	7.9	8.3	6.6	11.2
Optimized (invariants)	36.8	27	39.22	6.74	7.59	4.63	11.2
optimized (curve fitting)	40.6	25.5	31.3	7.9	8.3	6.3	12.1

CONCLUSION

An optimization overall process has been developed for determining the complex stiffness matrix of an orthotropic viscoelastic material. Classical processes (curve fitting) are applied only to elastic materials and optimize successively the elastic moduli. It is expected that this method may be improved when data in the three coordinate planes are available. Finally it would be necessary to compare the results with another test procedures: tensile test, low frequency vibrations, surface acoustic waves [8].

Figure 4. Contact technique Schematic.

Figure 5. Immersion technique. Schematic.

Figure 6. Coordinate system

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